

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you so much for the valuable comments from the anonymous reviewer on our article!

APPENDIX

A. Abstract

MICPAT source code is available at <https://gitlab.com/williamwp/micpat> with support for the recent main extension. Our artifact provides a workflow to apply MICPAT to CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL, or CUDA-Fortran applications and MICPAT is applicable to NVIDIA GPU architecture series including Kepler, Maxwell, Pascal and Volta in X86-64 and ARM64 architecture.

B. Artifact Checklist

- Program: CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL, or CUDA-Fortran programs built for Linux.
- Compilation: NVIDIA Driver 450.191. Driver needs to support CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL, or CUDA-Fortran programs and LD_PRELOAD environment variable.
- Hardware: For profiling CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL, or CUDA-Fortran case studies, one of the NVIDIA GPU architecture series including Kepler, Maxwell, Pascal and Volta required.
- Output: The data of microarchitecture-independent characteristics including basic blocks number for each kernel, CPU and GPU, each SASS instruction which can consist of instruction mix and instruction frequency.
- How much disk space required (approximately)?: The whole experiment environment and CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL, or CUDA-Fortran applications need less than 10 GB of space.
- How much time is needed to prepare workflow (approximately)?: less than 1 minute.
- How much time is needed to complete experiments (approximately)?: less than 1 minute.
- Publicly available?: Yes.

C. Description

- Hardware Dependencies: GPU and NVIDIA Driver version which is compatible with Kepler, Maxwell, Pascal and Volta must support CUDA, OpenACC, OpenCL and CUDA-Fortran programs.
- Software Dependencies: GPU must install CUDA toolkit version above 10.

D. Installation

- 1) Download from <https://gitlab.com/williamwp/micpat>
- 2) Follow README instructions to clone and build.

E. Experiment Workflow

To execute experiment, execute
LD_PRELOAD=./tools/basic_block/basic_block.so ./test-application/vectoradd. And then users will get the available data

on the terminal such as the numbers of basic block numbers for each kernel.

F. Evaluation and Expected Result

To evaluate the artifact, it is sufficient to run the experimental workflow and then graph the results. For instance, if users execute LD_PRELOAD=./tools/instr_frequency/instr_frequency.so ./test-application/vectoradd, users need to collect each instruction executing number in different kernels and put these instructions in different categories like Floating Point, Integer, Vector, Conversion, Movement, Predicate, Texture, Compute Load/Store Instructions, Surface Memory, Control and Miscellaneous depending the PASCAL SASS instruction set.